

OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVING THE THEORETICAL BASIS OF USING TESTOLOGY IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM

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Annotation: In this article, it is necessary to take into account many factors and take into account the socio-pedagogical environment and conditions when evaluating the educational achievements of students. Today, the need to modernize pedagogical measures and introduce international programs in education is increasing. The main goal of international assessment programs is to provide feedback on how students apply the knowledge they learn at school in everyday life.

Key words and phrases: modern society, independent education, modern worldview, social necessity, digital economy, evaluation process, innovative and digital, market economy, Education and training, scientific and methodical.

In the era of global changes, the development trends of the education quality assessment system at different levels, the participation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international comparative programs on the assessment of education quality are considered as an opportunity to increase the potential of the education system. Comprehensive analysis of the results of international comparative programs for the assessment of the quality of education, assessment of students' reading, natural sciences, mathematical thinking and creative thinking, in the creation of national teaching-methodical and measurement materials from the methodology and evaluation criteria of international programs will encourage use.

Through education, a new generation capable of fulfilling future tasks will be formed in the society. There are international programs for evaluating the educational achievements of students that determine the quality, level and level of education in the world, and they are widely used as the main criteria for further improving the quality of education in developed countries.

It is not possible to directly see the level of knowledge of the learner, the level of formation of skills, qualifications and competences: the teacher can see and measure them directly (through question-answering, observation, completing tasks). Certain decisions are made based on the results of such measurements.

Validity is the most basic concept that determines the quality of a test. Validity refers to the scientific and empirical validity of the conclusions drawn

from the test results based on the purpose of the test. Therefore, the conclusions made on the basis of the test results and the decisions made on the basis of this conclusion should be based.

Despite the fact that validity is the most basic concept of pedagogical measurements (testology), there was no consensus among experts on the definition of this concept. In order for us to be able to draw reasonable (valid) conclusions based on the test and make the right decisions based on these conclusions, the organizations involved in creating the test, conducting it, and processing its results must provide several proofs of validity.

In order to provide evidence related to the content of the test, the content of the test and the construct that should be measured with the help of the test are analyzed.

Several principles should be taken into account when determining the content of the test:[1]

- compliance of the test content with the purpose of the test
- importance of tested knowledge - important elements of science are included in the test.
- the correctness of the content of the test tasks - only the correct data should be entered into the test, and it is not possible to enter the wrong data into the test.
- the content of the test reflects the current level of development of the science - the test does not include outdated, obsolete information.
- comprehensiveness and proper balance of the test content - the test should cover all important elements of the examined domain.
- that the content of the test is a representative reflection of the content of the subject - there may be enough test subjects to evaluate each element included in the examined domain and make a reasonable conclusion about it.
- the systematicity of the content of the test - the tasks included in the test must systematically reflect the content of the subject;
- dependence of the test form on the test content;
- variability of the content of the test - if the test is held on different days, parallel test forms can be used so that the test tasks are not known in advance to the test takers.

Pedagogical test is a set of test tasks that allows to objectively determine the level of preparation of examinees in certain fields of knowledge [2]. In the development of pedagogical test materials, they should be developed based on the theory of pedagogical dimensions and the rules of testology in the process of

its creation and application, not in the form of a simple assignment, that is, in the form of presenting questions and answers [3]. The introduction of test assignments based on the rules of testology into the educational process allows for an objective assessment of the problems in the educational process. The scientific and methodical literature on the problems of test tests offers various classifications of pedagogical tests, as well as the main forms of test tasks and the general requirements for the design of test tasks.

The most common type of pedagogical tests are test tasks consisting of one correct answer, in which test tasks are created according to the main sections or topics of the studied subject. With the help of a structured test, students' level of mastery of educational material is checked during the test and their knowledge and skills are determined. The list of knowledge and skills planned for the test may include mastering the conceptual apparatus of the studied subject, knowledge of concrete facts, the ability to explain, generalize, systematize the studied material, and other similar requirements. In pedagogical literature, efforts are being made to develop a classification of educational goals that should be taken into account when planning educational content and specialties. In the literature, depending on the method of creating pedagogical test tasks, they are divided into four forms: [3] closed test task; open test assignment; such as the matching task and the correct sequencing task. We will cover this in detail through the table below.

All specified forms of test tasks can be used when creating a test option, but it is recommended to choose the same form when creating a test option for the final test to assess knowledge.

Case-study assignments and difficulty levels of productive, semi-exploratory and creative (creative) tests, which are included in the content of educational courses, play an important role in the creation and development of students' experiences of creative activity. It should be noted that one of the main methods of qualimetry in the control and assessment of the acquired knowledge, skills, skills and competences of students in the educational process is the use of test tasks, the inclusion of standard and non-standard test tasks in the control structure. must

Taking into account the above points, there is a need to use non-standard test tasks in addition to standard test tasks to determine the level of mastery of all components of the educational content by students.

One of the types of control used by students to determine the main components of the educational content is test tasks, and in order to form them

appropriately and use them in their place, it is necessary to know the theoretical basis of this process.

The organization of the educational process and the determination of its effectiveness are of great importance in the control and diversification of its types.

The educational process is a holistic system, its organization, progress control, analysis of the teacher's pedagogical activity according to the obtained results, identification of typical deficiencies in the acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications of students according to the rating system, and requires defining the ways of their correction.

One of the types of control in determining and evaluating students' acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in the courses included in the curriculum is the test tasks. Test tasks belong to the series of didactic materials, which perform the following functions:

Educational function of test assignments. The test assignments identify typical deficiencies in students' acquired knowledge, skills, and abilities, and encourage them to study the fundamentals of science in a regular and systematic manner in order to gain their knowledge.

Educational function of test tasks. Qualities that pave the way for perfection in students by making test tasks feel certain cognitive difficulties in the process of finding the right answer, performing mental operations in order to solve the problem: analysis, synthesis, comparison, generalization and drawing conclusions: will, conscious discipline, certain provides an opportunity to develop as a person by mobilizing to solve educational problems, endurance, patience, using knowledge and energy to achieve achievements.

Test assignments encourage students to develop their own knowledge, skills, and abilities, and take into account the importance of their share in the achieved results, realizing their responsibility in their future activities.

The test task used in the educational process should be created on the basis of four levels of difficulty, and the difficulty level of each task should be indicated in the passport of the task:

Easy (reproductive) (I) - a level that requires students to know the essence of events, events, laws and terms, which determines their ability to remember, without processing the educational material;

Moderately difficult (productive) (II) - a level that requires students to analyze, synthesize, compare objects, draw conclusions by applying several laws and regulations at the same time and generalizing;

Difficult (partially researched) (III) - applying previously acquired knowledge, skills and abilities by students in new unexpected situations, by analyzing objects, synthesizing, comparing, applying laws and regulations, and generalizing a level that requires inference;

The most difficult (creative) (IV) - mental operations such as applying previously acquired knowledge, skills and abilities by students in solving educational problems that arise in unexpected situations, analysis, synthesis, comparative comparison, generalization, conclusion level that requires performance.

Testologists associate the quality of the test materials with the quality of the test materials, and recommend the use of such test items in educational tests and especially in final control tests. However, the quality of the test materials, the test assignments developed by the test makers, must go through several stages, such as checking, testing, discussions, and recommendations of specialist experts. Test items that meet these requirements are approved under the same conditions and their results are evaluated by statistical analysis using statistical methods used in testology.

In the conditions of higher education, when groups of students make up 30 people and it is not possible to answer questions with all students during the seminar lesson, it is appropriate to use the test at the end of the seminar lesson. In this case, the proposed test options should include no more than 10 questions on the studied topic, and accordingly, 7-10 minutes will be allocated for their implementation. Tests used in seminars should not have too many questions.

It is very important to consider the time factor here. In this regard, it is appropriate to mention that the examinee usually needs 1 to 2 minutes (depending on the complexity of the task) to complete each test task. The above-mentioned issues should be taken into account when planning the use of tests during the workshop. To what extent the students learned their independent education with the help of the test

Discussion (Obsujdenie/Discussion). In New Uzbekistan, the National Center for the Implementation of International Programs was established under the State Inspectorate for Quality Control of Education. The main tasks and directions of activity of the National Center are as follows:

— participating as a national representative of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the organization and coordination of international evaluation programs and competitions;

- ensuring the coordination of the activities of state and non-state organizations in the development of literacy and the ability of young people to apply their knowledge in practice;
- carrying out scientific research aimed at the development and implementation of innovative methods of developing the level of knowledge of reading, mathematics and natural sciences in the educational system;
- establishment of international relations, development and implementation of international projects in the field of education quality assessment;
- participation in the organization and holding of international scientific conferences, symposiums;
- conducting fundamental and practical programs in the field of education quality assessment;
- Comparative evaluation of the quality of education in Uzbekistan and other countries of the world;
- scientific and methodological support for educational quality assessment programs;
- conducting systematic monitoring of the introduction of international assessment programs into the educational process, popularizing best practices in this field and participating in the production of recommendations and manuals for educational institutions based on it;
- conducting constant monitoring based on objective assessment and international comparison of the level of education of students;
- international comparison of educational system development trends;
- preparation of educational and methodological recommendations for the mother tongue, mathematics and natural sciences using innovative methods of teaching.

Participation in international education quality assessment programs gives Uzbekistan the following opportunities:

- the results obtained in the programs allow to draw conclusions about the quality of education in the country and its place taking into account international standards;
- the results are used in the reform of the national education system, the improvement of the content of education, the training of pedagogues and their professional development programs, and the creation of a new generation of textbooks by specialists;

– international programs have a positive effect on the quality of national programs in the field of education;

– By participating in international programs involving leading experts of various organizations in Uzbekistan, the culture of conducting monitoring programs among local experts develops, which leads to the adaptation of education quality assessment to international standards;

– allows development of control materials for national education quality assessment at the level of quality of control materials used in international programs. Also, participation in this program will stimulate the development of comparative programs in pedagogical programs. In addition, internationally used terms are widely introduced. The results of the program will definitely contribute to economic growth, and will lead to the creation of a large database in the preparation of long-term plans in the country's socio-economic and political spheres.

In the international program for the assessment of students' educational achievements, when studying the rating of higher education institutions, attention is paid to categorization taking into account factors such as their specialization, location, the quality of education depends not only on the teacher-student relationship, but also on the environment and conditions. dependence, the teacher should define goals that develop the students' skills of applying the topics to life in the formation of the work plan, psychologically support and motivate teachers, not for the purpose of punishing HEIs with low performance in the results of international programs, but on the contrary to be considered as an assistant in obtaining analytical data that will help in the implementation of reforms in the education system, students

Increasing the international competitiveness of education in Uzbekistan, introducing modern educational technologies, new methods of teaching and education in the educational system, focusing on increasing the interest and motivation of students to study. is becoming one of the priority areas of education. It is planned to build new universities in the regions, to reconstruct them, to strengthen their material and technical base, and at the same time to update educational standards. It is recommended to pay special attention to and use international best practices, including the requirements of international programs, when updating educational standards.

One of the goals of evaluating students' educational achievements is to research the ability of students to be observant, eager to learn and apply the knowledge they have learned in higher education institutions in different

situations and situations in everyday life. Of course, the selection of such tasks as program tasks is accepted by experts as correct, first of all, from an economic point of view. Issues, problems or situations in professional activity, independent life are complex and require the application of a number of knowledge, experience and skills.

The basic competencies of students are divided into two types:

- 1) competencies that can be assessed;
- 2) competencies that cannot be assessed.

Assessment programs do not provide an opportunity to quantitatively measure, observe, and compare the components that make up the basic competencies of students. In particular, it is impossible to measure a student's motivation, interest, aspiration, imagination, approach, as well as social competence. An important aspect that can be observed from the history of the programs presented in the first chapter of the work is that the standards always choose methods that can be measured in precise numbers in a short period of time. Above are the three main core terms used in the program, and their analysis also shows that it is possible to measure the main elements of the core competencies in concrete numbers only through assignments. The rest of the elements can be determined qualitatively, in percentages, based on contextual indicators. Contextual indicators are seen as conditions for the formation of the student's basic competencies. In particular, the questionnaires designed for students, teachers, parents and management of higher education institutions in the program analyze the conditions for the formation of basic basic competencies.

The analysis of the literature shows that the persons responsible for education of the countries participating in the program analyze these conditions in many ways, and on this basis, they develop new concepts for improving the literacy of students in the next program.

The role of the labor market in the educational system of the developed United States of America, England, Germany, and Japan is clearly noticeable. As the labor market's demands for labor resources and its quality grow, the educational system adapts to meet these demands. The requirements of the labor market have been formed as the goal of education. As the labor market is a direct "orderer" of specialists needed by the educational system, the labor market has formed the requirements for the specialists of the educational system. The educational system, adapting to the labor market, has incorporated these requirements into the educational standards. The organization of the

educational process, the content of the educational process, the applied methods and the didactics of the subjects are being adjusted to the competencies required in the labor market.

The famous philosopher Seneca's sentence "Non scholae, sed vitae discimus" [5] (you should study for life, not for higher education) indicated the main goal of education. Development of knowledge and skills that are important for life, formation of knowledge and skills that will be necessary in the future life of the student is the task of HEIs.

Digitization (the transfer of information into digital form) is turning many into 'consumers', and in turn, interest in knowledge and skills is waning. It is the main task of HE education in the current era that students find their direction in life. From this point of view, the task of higher education institutions is not only to impart knowledge, but also to form the ability of students to independently search for information using digital technologies and to present it. The introduction of social changes and problems as assignments in the educational process strengthens the interest of students. It is the task of the Higher Education Institution to resolve changes and problems in educational groups in an official state with various methods. The teacher acts as a moderator and provides sufficient information and assignments.

There are opinions in society that knowledge is obsolete and useless. This also affects students. All knowledge does not become old, on the contrary, it serves as a foundation for new knowledge. Competency approach in higher education institutions, without denying imparting knowledge, requires to focus on competencies aimed at practical application and use. The problem with this approach is that the training focuses more on the methodological aspect, which leads to a departure from the content. Students' attention to educational material and textbooks is relatively reduced. When working with a competency-based concept, the teacher of the present era is required to work more on the methodology and content. The large flow of information in the information society requires professional skills in finding materials that can attract students and be used for educational purposes.

Usually, it is appropriate to assess the student's acquisition of a certain competence and the stages of acquisition of this competence. On the other hand, one of the aspects of the existing evaluation system in the higher education system that needs to be improved is the need to analyze the evaluation process from a socio-psychological point of view. In the auditorium, in front of all students, the teacher openly informs students of their grades, and students

study only for a good grade, in turn, is contrary to the concept of competency-based teaching. It has been scientifically proven in many programs that students who receive unsatisfactory grades lose interest in science and have a negative effect on the student's morale.

The fact that assessment becomes the primary activity in the educational process prevents the realization of educational goals. There are several downsides to such frequent evaluations during student life. First of all, the student's confidence in himself and his success decreases. Problematic situations arise between students who get good and excellent grades compared to students who get unsatisfactory grades.

From the meaning of the term competence, it should be noted that the acquisition of competence is not only theoretical knowledge, but also the ability to apply that knowledge in different situations, situations, and certain conditions. It is one of the main requirements for the student to understand the problem situation, to be able to plan the solution methods, to implement it based on the plan and to be able to evaluate his solution, as well as to do all the listed stages voluntarily.

One of the users of the evaluation system is the parents of the students. The current assessment system does not reflect the competencies that students should acquire in the state education standards. It is more important for a parent to know which parts of competences are lacking in the acquisition of their child's grades and to give pedagogical recommendations to eliminate this deficiency. Effective integration of education, science and production in targeted and high-quality training of personnel is defined as the tasks of state education standards. The evaluation system should be integrated with the evaluation system in science and production as part of the educational process [5]. It is known that intermediate and final results, as well as the quality of process organization, are evaluated in science and production.

It is desirable that the correct implementation of the evaluation system in HEIs should be based on general competencies related to the subject and subject. All competencies are listed in the education standard and qualification requirements.[6] A comprehensive assessment of the level of achievement of each competency requirement is more beneficial to the student and parent in many ways. In this way, it is transferred to the competency-based assessment system.

The level of competencies acquired in the state education standards of the Republic of Uzbekistan includes A1, A2, B1, B2, S1 and S2 levels. Criteria for each

level have been developed. These levels have the same content as the assessment. Therefore, instead of daily and continuous assessment, graded assessment based on educational standards is more appropriate in many ways. The grade is not a clear criterion that determines knowledge in the educational process, but is a tool that motivates and encourages students to be active. The criteria by which teachers evaluate students has always been a controversial topic.[7]

Evaluation is always a cause of debate in the education system and education policy. In many countries, such as Finland, which achieves high results in international assessment programs, students are not assessed. In Germany, students are not evaluated in primary grades. Student assessment programs have been in place for several years. There are conclusions that evaluation based on the results of the programs is not fair, mistakes are made in the evaluation, and it has a negative impact on the students' learning. The activity of the teacher goes directly in parallel with the evaluation process. If we generalize the perception of schools in society, evaluation has always been the main topic. This, in turn, serves as a tool in the state's educational policy and at the same time as an indicator of the quality of state education. For this purpose, internal and external monitoring is conducted in each educational institution during the academic year. According to its results, the rating of schools, the potential of teachers and the literacy of students are determined. Grade registers contain comprehensive information for teacher, student and parent and have more functionality than grades.

The methods of organizing and determining the ratings of educational institutions are different and are directly related to the educational systems of the countries and the methods of evaluating higher education. Currently, a number of foreign countries, including the United States of America, Great Britain, Germany, Poland, the Netherlands, Spain, Japan, China, Russia, and Ukraine, have rich experience in determining and applying the rating of educational institutions. . Their existing rating systems were developed based on different approaches based on the characteristics of educational systems.

In the United States, three groups of quality indicators are used for ranking: student success, faculty achievement, and HEI academic capabilities. The weighting and summation method is used to convert these indicators into a rating.

In the UK, the rating is determined by the media based on data from statistical sources. Among the indicators, attention is also paid to scientific

works. The opinions of personnel consumers about the educational institution are considered as one of the main indicators.

Higher education institutions in Poland are ranked separately, taking into account their characteristics (general universities, private universities, creative universities). In the rating, the results of the previous year's rating are also taken into account with a certain weight. The rating of private universities is determined on the basis of surveys conducted directly at the university and among employers and teachers. The ranking of universities in Japan is carried out mainly in 3 directions: educational activity, scientific research activity and contribution to development. Recently, student surveys are also widely used. In conclusion, we can say that pedagogues-teachers have their own views and opinions on the development of pedagogical tests. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the special textbooks on the development of test tasks, the approaches proposed by the authors of scientific articles, the requirements and proposals. This helps to analyze the results obtained in the tests, to identify achievements and shortcomings in the development of test tasks.

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